

Agronomic characteristics of newly released varieties in Nepal.

Agronomic characteristic	Varieties					
	Kanchan (IR3941)	Himali (IR2298)	Taichung 176 (check)	Malika (Mala/J 15)	CH-45 (check)	Laxmi (check)
Days to heading	103	110	103	90	85	95
Days to maturity	143	145	148	120	115	125
Plant height (cm)	68	61	84	119	124	95
Panicle length (cm)	21	22	21	22.3	26.0	21.0
Panicle no./m ²	400	275	265	305	340	405
No. of filled grains/panicle	81	91	90	108	73	73
Fertility (%)	82	91	78	85	88	89
1,000-grain wt (g)	22.1	26.9	24.5	21.3	25.0	24.9
Straw wt (t/ha)	5.81	5.38	6.07	—	—	—
Blast reaction	R	R	S	S	R	R
Unhusked length (mm)	9.6	10.3	7.8	8.5	8.9	9.2
Unhusked width (mm)	3.4	3.4	3.5	2.8	2.9	2.9
Shape	Slender/long	Slender	Medium/short	Slender/med.	Slender/long	Slender/long
% of husking	78.37	75.22	80.22	78.1	77.5	78.6
% of milling	72.50	72.00	76.00	72.4	71.5	73.0
Appearance of polished rice	High/trans.	High/trans.	Medium/low with white belly	High/trans.	Coarse with white belly	Medium with white belly
Av yield	7.60	7.18	6.40	4.9	4.3	4.58
Testing station	Khumaltar Kathmandu	Khumaltar Kathmandu	Khumaltar Kathmandu	Parwanipur	Parwanipur	Parwanipur

Nepal, three rice varieties were released for general cultivation by the national seed recommendation committee of Nepal in 1982 (see table). IR3941-4-PLP2B (CR126-42-5/IR2061-213), which was named Kanchan, and IR2298-PLPB-3-2-1-1-B (CICA 4/ Kulu), which was named Himali, are recommended for temperate regions up to

1,500 m altitude. Mala/J15 (CP-SL02/ Sigadis), which was named Malika, is suitable as an early crop in irrigated areas and a monsoon season crop in rainfed tropical areas.

Kanchan and Himali are high yielding and blast resistant. They have early maturity and good eating quality and are easily threshable. They are as non-

lodging as the Taiwanese varieties grown in the Kathmandu valley and in areas of similar climates in temperate Nepal. Himali is an aromatic variety with good market value.

Malika is early and resistant to lodging. It has high seed dormancy during rainy season harvesting, bacterial blight resistance, and good grain quality. ■

Evaluation of IRTP nurseries

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Two trials — International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) and the International Rainfed Lowland Rice Observational Nursery (IRLRON) — were conducted during 1981 kar (Jun-Nov). The nonreplicated observational plots were not protected from pests and diseases. For IRON, 242 genetically diverse entries and 5 checks were screened. For IRLRON, 128 entries (38 early and 90 late duration) and 7 checks were evaluated. Cultivars were sown on 18 June 1981 and transplanted on 17 July. Plot sizes were 3.25 m × 0.75 m with 25- × 25-cm spacing, 1 seedling/hill. The fertilizer schedule was 100-50-50 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha.

For IRON, IR13540-56-3-2-1 (R.

Table 1. Performance of promising entries from the 8th IRON, Tamil Nadu, India.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)	% over ADT36 (local check)	Flowering duration (days)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>Entry</i>				
IR9763-11-2-2-3	5.5	100.0	105	94
IR9830-26-3-3	7.0	127.3	103	83
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	5.7	103.6	96	89
IR15529-256-1	5.5	100.0	95	84
IR17525-278-1-1-2	5.7	103.6	104	86
IR19588-162-1	6.2	112.7	105	92
343 DT	6.2	112.7	95	100
BKNBR 1031-7-5-4	5.7	103.6	105	146
BR161-2B-54	6.6	120.0	99	87
B2791-B-MR-145-1	5.5	100.0	105	131
B3063-B-TK-72-2	6.0	109.1	103	110
Chianung Si-Pi. 661020	5.5	100.0	98	93
IR5657-33-2-2-3	6.4	116.4	98	108
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	6.1	110.9	95	110
IR13149-71-3-2	5.9	107.3	105	108
IR19661-293-1-3-2	5.5	100.0	98	96
IR19670-57-1-1-3	7.0	127.3	97	103
Kaohsiung Sen Yu 104	5.9	107.3	95	104
MTU 7029	6.6	120.0	105	105
OR47-2 (Jajati)	7.4	134.5	95	122
OR131-3-1	6.6	120.0	100	88
RP 1057-184-5-3-3	5.5	100.0	125	116
R 35-2874	6.4	116.4	95	95
Suakoko 8(2526)	6.0	109.1	100	134
X 2-D T	5.9	107.3	95	92

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Table 1 continued

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)	% over ADT36 (local check)	Flowering duration (days)	Plant ht (cm)
Chianung Sen Yu 13	5.9	107.3	96	94
IR13540-56-3-2-1	7.8	141.8	91	75
RP825-45-1-3	6.2	112.7	100	84
<i>Check</i>				
IR36	3.0	54.5	95	82
BR10(BR51-46-5)	3.9	70.9	104	105
IR42	3.3	60.0	106	82
IR1552	1.4	25.5	98	83
ADT36 (local)	5.5	100.0	96	101
Mean (m)	4.2	76.4		
Std. deviation (σ)	1.2	21.8		
m + σ	5.4	98.2		

Table 2. Performance of promising entries from the 4th IRLRON, Tamil Nadu, India.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)	% of Pelita I-1 (local check)	Flowering duration (days)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>Entry</i>				
BR10(BR51-46-5)	4.8	123.1	99	113
IR13146-45-2	5.5	141.0	96	121
IR13505-30-B-3	4.8	123.1	89	86
IR4744-295-2-3	4.7	120.5	92	87
IR5873-9-1	5.0	128.2	89	106
IR9763-11-2-2-3	4.7	120.5	99	106
BIET927 (RAU 38-12-3-1)	4.5	115.4	123	146
BKN6990-63	5.0	128.2	119	157
BR111-140-1-1	4.5	115.4	114	148
CR1030	6.4	164.1	116	151
C424-2	4.5	115.4	106	124
IR13365-253-3-2	4.5	115.4	117	111
IR13564-109-1	4.7	120.5	116	100
IR14632-65-2	4.5	115.4	116	112
IR14875-98-5	4.5	115.4	113	104
IR19083-22-2-2	4.5	115.4	118	104
IR19431-72-2	5.4	138.5	103	94
IR3646-9-1-1	4.8	123.1	99	132
IR4819-77-3-2	5.4	138.5	106	133
IR4829-89-2	4.8	123.1	112	115
IR5857-64-IE-1-6	4.7	120.5	110	108
IR7545-27-3-2	4.7	120.5	106	100
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	5.7	146.2	105	116
IR9763-11-2-2-3	4.5	115.4	106	109
KAU 2039	4.7	120.5	104	128
MR24	4.5	115.4	98	108
<i>Check</i>				
IR36	3.6	92.3	87	76
Cisadane	3.6	92.3	105	108
Mashuri	2.9	74.4	107	139
IR46	2.7	69.2	115	93
IR1552	1.6	41.0	105	75
IR20	2.9	74.4	98	127
Pelita I-1 (local)	3.9	100.0	103	114
Mean (m)	3.4	87.2		
Std. deviation (σ)	1.1	28.2		
m + σ	4.5	115.4		

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Heenati/IR30(BPHS)/IR2823-399-5) had the highest yield (7.8 t/ha in 121 days), 41.8% more than the local check (Table 1). Yields of 30 other entries and ADT36 ranged from 5.4 to 7.0 t/ha.

For IRLRON, CR1030 (Waikoku/CR 1014-211) had the highest yield (6.4 t/ha in 146 days), 64.1% more than the best check (Table 2). Yields of 24 other entries ranged from 4.5 to 5.5 t/ha.

The only insect observed during the season was whorl maggot, within a threshold level of 20%. There was no disease incidence. Based on grain yield and ancillary characters, 28 entries from IRON and 3 entries from IRLRON, all of medium duration, have been selected for further testing. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Resistance of rice cultivars to *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at seedling and adult stages

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The clipping method was used to inoculate 20-day-old seedlings of 428 cultivars with a highly virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Average lesion lengths of the seedling leaves were recorded 15 days after inoculation. Adult stage damage was rated on the standard evaluation scale for rice (0-4 resistant and 4.1-9 susceptible).

Thirteen cultivars showed resistance at both seedling and adult stages (see table). Cultivars carrying *Xa 1*, *Xa 2*, *Xa 3*, and *xa 5* were resistant at seedling as well as the adult stage. IR20 carrying the gene *Xa 4* was susceptible at both stages.

Some cultivars showed resistance at the seedling stage only — ARC 6172, ARC 6181, ARC 6615, ARC 7251, B-76, IR15529-26-1-1-2, IR15529-253-2-2-2, NCS-2003, NCS 2014, NCS 2039,